

MODERN APPROACHES TO THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF BENIGN PROSTATIC HYPERPLASIA

Shukrullo Nabidzhonov Azizjon ugli

Master's student at the Central Asian Medical University.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20721030>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 12th June 2026

Accepted: 14th June 2026

Online: 16th June 2026

KEYWORDS

benign prostatic hyperplasia, BPH, prostate, prostate-specific antigen (PSA), uroflowmetry, transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP), laser enucleation, minimally invasive urology, quality of life

ABSTRACT

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is one of the most common urological diseases among elderly men. The aim of this study was to investigate modern methods for the diagnosis and treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia and to evaluate their clinical effectiveness. A total of 150 patients aged 50 to 82 years with BPH were examined and treated. The results demonstrated the high diagnostic value of a comprehensive assessment including prostate-specific antigen (PSA) testing, ultrasonographic examination, and uroflowmetry. Modern pharmacological and minimally invasive treatment methods contributed to significant improvements in urodynamic parameters and patients' quality of life.

Relevance. Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is one of the most common diseases of the male genitourinary system. According to the World Health Organization, signs of BPH are found in more than 50% of men over 60 years of age and in 80–90% of men over 80 years of age. An increase in the volume of the prostate gland is accompanied by a violation of urination, a deterioration in the quality of life and an increased risk of developing complications from the urinary tract.

The development of BPH is accompanied by lower urinary tract symptoms, including increased urinary frequency, nocturia, weakened urinary stream, a sensation of incomplete bladder emptying, and urinary retention. These disorders significantly reduce patients' quality of life and can lead to chronic urinary retention, urinary tract infections, stone formation, and renal failure.

In recent years, the widespread adoption of modern diagnostic and treatment methods has significantly improved the outcomes of patients with BPH. However, early diagnosis, optimal treatment options, and complication prevention remain challenging.

Purpose of the study. To study modern methods of diagnosis and treatment of benign prostatic hyperplasia and evaluate their clinical effectiveness in patients of different age groups.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted in the urology department of a multidisciplinary clinic in Fergana between 2021 and 2024.

The study included 150 patients with clinically and instrumentally confirmed benign prostatic hyperplasia. The subjects ranged in age from 50 to 82 years, with an average age of 66.8 ± 1.4 years. Distribution of patients by age groups: 50–59 years old - 38 patients (25.3%); 60–69 years old - 62 patients (41.3%); 70–82 years old - 50 patients (33.4%).

All patients underwent the following: collection of complaints and anamnesis; digital rectal examination; determination of PSA level; transabdominal and transrectal ultrasound examination; uroflowmetry; determination of residual urine volume; assessment of symptoms using the IPSS scale; assessment of quality of life using the QoL scale.

The patients were divided into two groups:

Group I (n=92) — conservative therapy: α 1-adrenergic blockers; 5- α -reductase inhibitors; combination therapy.

Group II (n=58) — surgical treatment: transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP); laser enucleation of the prostate; bipolar plasma vaporization.

Treatment outcomes were assessed at 6 and 12 months of follow-up.

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS Statistics 23.0. Mean values ($M \pm m$), Pearson correlation coefficients (r), and the level of statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) were calculated.

Results. Before treatment, most patients complained of increased urination frequency, nocturia, difficulty urinating and decreased quality of life.

After the treatment, a significant improvement in urodynamic and clinical parameters was noted (Table 1).

Table 1

Main clinical and functional indicators of patients before and after treatment ($M \pm m$)

Indicator	Before treatment	After treatment	p
Maximum urine flow rate (Qmax), ml/s	8,1±0,5	18,7±0,8	<0,001
Residual urine volume, ml	92,4±6,1	28,6±3,4	<0,001
Prostate gland volume, cm ³	58,7±2,8	42,1±2,2	<0,001
IPSS, points	23,4±1,2	8,6±0,7	<0,001
QoL, points	5,2±0,3	1,9±0,2	<0,001
PSA level, ng/ml	4,8±0,3	3,1±0,2	<0,01

The results indicate a significant improvement in urination and a reduction in the severity of disease symptoms. A strong correlation was found between prostate volume, symptom severity, and patient quality of life. The study demonstrated that a comprehensive diagnostic approach enables the timely detection of BPH and the determination of optimal treatment strategies. PSA testing, combined with ultrasound and uroflowmetry, was found to be highly informative in assessing patients with lower urinary tract symptoms.

Conservative therapy proved effective in patients with moderate symptoms and small prostate volumes. However, in patients with significantly enlarged prostates and severe bladder outlet obstruction, better results were achieved with surgical treatment. The most

significant improvement in urodynamic parameters was observed after transurethral resection and laser enucleation of the prostate, which is consistent with the data of modern scientific literature.

Conclusions:

1. Benign prostatic hyperplasia remains one of the most common urological pathologies in older men;
2. Comprehensive diagnostics using PSA, ultrasound, and uroflowmetry ensures high accuracy in diagnosing BPH;
3. After treatment, significant improvements in urodynamic parameters and quality of life are observed in patients ($p < 0.001$);
4. Maximum urine flow rate more than doubles after treatment;
5. Surgical treatments demonstrate the greatest effectiveness in cases of severe infravesical obstruction;
6. Individualized treatment strategies reduce the risk of complications and improve treatment effectiveness.

References:

1. Лопаткин Н.А. Урология. Национальное руководство. – М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа, 2023. – 1120 с.
2. Аляев Ю.Г., Глыбочко П.В. Урология. – М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа, 2023. – 768 с.
3. Пушкарь Д.Ю. Доброкачественная гиперплазия предстательной железы. – М.: Практическая медицина, 2022. – 384 с.
4. Аполихин О.И., Сивков А.В. Современные аспекты лечения ДГПЖ. Урология. 2023;4:5–12.
5. Gratzke C., Bachmann A., Descalzaud A. EAU Guidelines on Management of Non-neurogenic Male Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms. European Urology. 2024;86(2):178–198.
6. McVary K.T., Roehrborn C.G. Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia: Epidemiology and Clinical Management. Urologic Clinics of North America. 2023;50(1):1–15.
7. Foster H.E., Barry M.J., Dahm P. Surgical Management of Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms Attributed to Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia. Journal of Urology. 2023;210(4):742–756.
8. Roehrborn C.G. Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia: Etiology, Pathophysiology and Natural History. Campbell-Walsh-Wein Urology. 14th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier; 2024.